

Kinetics and mechanism of the osmium(VIII)-catalysed autoxidation of aqueous sulfur dioxide in acidic and alkaline media^ψ

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Kinetics of the osmium(VIII)-catalysed oxidation of sulfur(IV) by dioxygen in stirred solutions obeys the rate law (A) in phosphate buffered alkaline medium, and the rate law (B) in acetate buffered acidic medium.

$$R_{\text{obs}} = k[\text{Os}^{\text{VIII}}][\text{S}^{\text{IV}}][\text{OH}^-]^{-1} \quad (\text{A})$$

$$R_{\text{obs}} = k_3[\text{Os}^{\text{VIII}}][\text{S}^{\text{IV}}]^2[\text{H}^+]^{-1} \quad (\text{B})$$

The kinetics order in $[\text{O}_2]$ is zero. The rate is comparatively faster in alkaline medium. The proposed mechanisms involve the $\text{Os}^{\text{VIII}}/\text{Os}^{\text{VI}}$ cycle perpetuated by reduction of Os^{VIII} by S^{IV} , and regeneration of Os^{VIII} by oxidation of osmium(VI) by O_2 as cooxidant. There is spectrophotometric evidence for the formation of an intermediate complex in acid medium.

The atmospheric aqueous phase oxidation of the most important acid rain-precursor, sulfur dioxide, by dioxygen is one of the major causes of rain water acidification. This has led to a large number of studies on metal catalysed oxidation of sulfur(IV) by dioxygen, i.e. autoxidation.

Studies on the autoxidation of sulfur(IV) in the absence of any added catalyst are replete with diverse rate laws¹⁻⁶ and the pH dependences. This wide disagreement in the reported results has been linked to catalysis by trace metal ion. In fact, Huss *et al.*⁷ and others have shown⁸ the sulfur(IV) autoxidation to be completely arrested by addition of masking agents such as EDTA and 1,10-phenanthroline lending support to the notion that the uncatalyzed oxidation of aqueous S^{IV} by oxygen, if it at all occurs, must be very slow⁹. Among the trace metal ion catalysts, which influence the rate of sulfur(IV) autoxidation, the transition metal ions capable of forming multiple oxidation states have generally been found to be the most potent. Their catalytic activity results from their ability to form a variety of complexes and multiple oxidation states¹. Thus, the operation

of a catalytic cycle involving $\text{M}^{\text{n+}}/\text{M}^{(\text{n-1})+}$ or $\text{M}^{\text{n+}}/\text{M}^{(\text{n-2})+}$ oxidation states is possible.

During the last three decades, several homogeneous autoxidation studies using metal ions^{1,9-17} such as Fe^{II} , Fe^{III} , Cu^{II} ¹², Mn^{II} ¹⁴, Co^{II} and their complexes have been carried out and the general mechanistic features of catalysis are now well understood. Although, platinum group metal are known to influence a variety of chemical reactions¹⁸, there is hardly any study using any of these metals as catalysts for the oxidation of aqueous sulfur dioxide, i.e. sulfur(IV), by oxygen¹⁸. This led us to study the catalytic oxidation of sulfite by oxygen using trace concentrations of osmium(VIII) in both acid and alkaline media. Incidentally, osmium(VIII) has been extensively used as catalyst in the oxidation of a large number of organic and inorganic compounds¹⁹⁻²³.

Experimental

Osmium tetroxide, OsO_4 , (Johnson Matthey) and all other chemicals of reagent grade were used. OsO_4 solution

^ψDedicated to Professor Y. K. Gupta on his 80th birth anniversary.

was prepared by dissolving it in 0.5 mol dm⁻³ NaOH solution. It was analysed iodometrically and stored in a refrigerator. For studies in acid media, 10 ml of acetate buffer containing appropriate volumes of 2.0 mol dm⁻³ CH₃COOH and 2.0 mol dm⁻³ CH₃COONa for a total 100 ml reaction mixture were used. Likewise, for studies in alkaline phosphate buffered media, 10 ml of buffer containing appropriate volumes of 0.5 mol dm⁻³ Na₂HPO₄ and 1.0 mol dm⁻³ of KH₂PO₄ for a total 100 ml reaction mixture were used. The procedure for studying the kinetics was same as described earlier²⁴⁻²⁶. The reactions were conducted in thermostated Erlenmeyer flasks and the reaction mixture was continuously stirred at 1500 ± 100 rpm to save the reaction from becoming oxygen mass transfer controlled. The reactions were initiated by adding sodium sulfite and osmium(VIII) solutions, in that order, to the reaction mixture containing buffer.

The treatment of kinetics results obtained in this study is based on the determination of initial rates, *R*_{obs}, which were reproducible to within ±10%.

Results and discussion

Stoichiometry of osmium(VIII)-catalysed autoxidation :

In oxidation by oxygen, i.e. autoxidation only trace amounts of osmium(VIII) were used. In both acidic and alkaline media, sulfate was the only oxidation product of sulfite. For quantitative analysis, the reaction mixture containing known concentration of sodium sulfite and known trace amount of osmium(VIII) was continuously stirred for a long time to ensure completion of the reaction. The sulfate was estimated gravimetrically by precipitating sulfate ions as BaSO₄ using standard procedure. The stoichiometric results (Table 1) were in agreement with the eq. (1).

Osmium(VIII)-sulfur(IV) reaction in N₂-atmosphere :

Since osmium(VIII) and sulfur(IV) are strong oxidant and

reductant respectively, the reaction between them is expected to be fast. Expectedly, sulfur(IV) is known to reduce *cis*-ester of osmium(VIII) and cyclopentene²⁷. Similarly SO₂ is reported to reduce osmium(VIII) in alkaline medium²⁸. In both cases, sulfite is oxidised to sulfate and osmium(VIII) is reduced to osmium(VI). The validity and applicability of these findings to our systems was checked as follows.

Deoxygenated osmium(VIII), sulfur(IV) and buffer solutions were prepared by continuously passing N₂. The desired amounts of these solutions were mixed, and immediately afterwards BaCl₂ solution was added. The amount of BaSO₄ precipitated was in accordance with eq. (2).

The results of spectrophotometric titrations performed by recording absorbance at 223 nm immediately after mixing deoxygenated reactants too were in conformity with eq. (2). These results lead to the conclusion that the reaction between osmium(VIII) and sulfur(IV) is indeed fast and that the osmium(VIII) is reduced to osmium(VI) stage only.

UV-visible spectra of osmium(VIII)-sulfur(IV) in N₂-atmosphere :

At first, the spectra were recorded in N₂-atmosphere. In acetate buffered medium, the addition of deoxygenated sulfur(IV) to deoxygenated osmium(VIII) resulted in the appearance of a peak at 265 nm (Fig. 1) which was absent in the spectrum of osmium(VIII) solution, when alone. Since osmium(VIII) is reduced, as pointed earlier, the peak is due to the complex formation between osmium(VI) and

Fig. 1. The spectra of S^{IV} (a), Os^{VIII} (b) and Os^{VIII}-S^{IV} (c) at pH = 5.22 and 30°C.

sulfur(IV). Using the method described²⁹, the stability constant of this complex was determined to be 37.5. Variation in pH had no observable effect on absorbance and this signifies that the complex is formed between osmium(VI) and HSO₃⁻, the dominant sulfur(IV) species in the pH range of this study in acetate buffered medium. This is in agreement with the formation of sulphitosmyl(VI) salts of the type

Table 1. Stoichiometry of osmium(VIII)-catalysed autoxidation of sulfur(IV)

10 ⁶ [Os ^{VIII}] mol dm ⁻³	10 ³ [S ^{IV}] mol dm ⁻³	pH	10 ³ [SO ₄ ²⁻] mol dm ⁻³	[SO ₄ ²⁻]/ [S ^{IV}]	[SO ₄ ²⁻] recovery in %
1.0	2.0	5.22	1.92	0.96	96
1.0	3.0	5.22	2.94	0.98	98
2.0	5.0	5.22	4.90	0.98	98
0.5	2.0	8.70	1.90	0.96	96
0.5	4.0	8.70	3.89	0.97	97
0.5	6.0	8.70	5.85	0.98	98

Table 2. R_{obs} values for osmium(VIII)-catalysed autoxidation of sulfur(IV) in alkaline medium at 30°C

$10^7 [\text{Os}^{\text{VIII}}]$ mol dm ⁻³	$10^3 [\text{S}^{\text{IV}}]$ mol dm ⁻³	pH	$10^7 R_{\text{obs}}$ mol dm ⁻³ s ⁻¹
3.0	0.5	8.78	0.98
4.0	0.5	8.78	1.20
5.0	0.5	8.78	1.39
7.0	0.5	8.78	1.75
8.0	0.5	8.78	2.00
2.0	2.0	8.78	2.75
4.0	2.0	8.78	4.50
6.0	2.0	8.78	6.00
8.0	2.0	8.78	7.85
10.0	2.0	8.78	9.50
2.0	4.0	8.78	5.0
4.0	4.0	8.78	8.0
6.0	4.0	8.78	12.5
8.0	4.0	8.78	15.5
10.0	4.0	8.98	19.0
1.0	2.0	8.78	1.75
1.0	4.0	8.78	3.50
1.0	5.0	8.78	3.75
1.0	8.0	8.78	6.50
1.0	10.0	8.78	8.02
2.0	2.0	8.78	2.50
2.0	4.0	8.78	5.00
2.0	5.0	8.78	6.00
2.0	8.0	8.78	9.80
2.0	10.0	8.78	11.2
5.0	1.0	8.78	2.50
5.0	2.0	8.78	5.00
5.0	7.0	8.78	15.5
5.0	9.0	8.78	20.0
5.0	10.0	8.78	22.0
1.0	0.5	9.00	1.05
1.0	0.5	8.69	2.25
1.0	0.5	8.61	2.50
1.0	0.5	8.52	3.00
1.0	0.5	8.33	5.25
1.0	2.0	8.78	5.30
1.0	2.0	8.60	7.80
1.0	2.0	8.39	12.5
1.0	2.0	8.35	14.0
1.0	2.0	8.30	16.0
2.0	1.0	9.00	5.00
2.0	1.0	8.78	9.20
2.0	1.0	8.71	11.0
2.0	1.0	8.60	13.7
2.0	1.0	8.40	21.5

$[\text{M}_2\text{O}_2(\text{SO}_3\text{M})_4]$ in which sulfur is monovalent²⁸. It is interesting to point out that the colour of the solution remained light yellow for a pretty long time in N_2 -atmosphere and increased on increasing osmium(VIII).

In alkaline medium, there was no change in absorbance on addition of sulfur(IV) to osmium(VIII) solution. As pointed out earlier, the rapid reaction between osmium(VIII) and sulfur(IV) in alkaline medium will result in the formation of osmium(VI). Obviously, no strong complex is formed between osmium(VI) and sulfur(IV), when the medium is alkaline.

UV-visible spectra of osmium(VIII)-sulfur(IV) in oxygenated solutions :

In oxygen containing acetate buffered solutions, when S^{IV} was added to Os^{VIII} solution (1×10^{-5} mol dm⁻³), a light pink colour appeared immediately. The spectra of this solution, which was recorded immediately (Fig. 2) after mixing osmium(VIII) and sulfur(IV), showed the formation of two new peaks at 385 nm and 500 nm in addition to one observed at 265 nm in N_2 -atmosphere. Within a few minutes, the solution turned blue and the absorbances at these two peaks were seen to increase (Fig. 5). The blue colour, which will mask pink colour, persisted till the end of the reaction, when all sulfite was exhausted.

Fig. 2. The spectra of $\text{Os}^{\text{VIII}}\text{-S}^{\text{IV}}\text{-O}_2$ system in stirred solution : (a) immediately after mixing, (b) after 10 min, (c) after 20 min, (d) after completion of the reaction.

Kinetics in phosphate buffered alkaline medium :

In all autoxidation kinetics studies, only trace amounts of osmium(VIII) were used. The rate of autoxidation increased on increasing stirring speed attaining a limiting value around 1500 ± 100 rpm. This implicates oxygen as an oxidant^{30,31}. Since its concentration in solution did not affect the rate of reaction as evidenced by similar rates in air-saturated and oxygen-saturated stirred solutions, a zero order in $[\text{O}_2]$ is established. The kinetics results of $[\text{Os}^{\text{VIII}}]$ and $[\text{S}^{\text{IV}}]$ variations (Table 2) at pH 8.78 obeyed the rate law (3).

$$R_{\text{obs}} = k_0[S^{\text{IV}}] + k_1[\text{Os}^{\text{VIII}}][S^{\text{IV}}] \quad (3)$$

where the term $k_0[S^{\text{IV}}]$ is due to uncatalysed reaction. From the linear plots of R_{obs} versus $[\text{Os}^{\text{VIII}}]$ (Fig. 3) and R_{obs} versus $[S^{\text{IV}}]$ (Fig. 4), the values of k_0 and k_1 were determined to be $4.5 \times 10^{-5} \text{ s}^{-1}$ and $3.7 \times 10^2 \text{ dm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ s}^{-1}$ respectively

Fig. 3. Variation of R_{obs} with $[\text{Os}^{\text{VIII}}]$ at different $[S^{\text{IV}}]$, pH = 8.78 and 30°C : (o) $[S^{\text{IV}}] = 5 \times 10^{-4} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$, (Δ) $[S^{\text{IV}}] = 2 \times 10^{-3} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$, (\bullet) $[S^{\text{IV}}] = 4 \times 10^{-3} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$.

at 8.78 pH and 30°C . The results of variation in pH in the range 7.90–8.80 were in agreement with the rate law (4).

$$R_{\text{obs}} = k_0 [S^{\text{IV}}] + \frac{k_2 [\text{Os}^{\text{VIII}}][S^{\text{IV}}]}{[\text{OH}^-]} \quad (4)$$

where, $k_2/[\text{OH}^-] = k_1$

As required by eq. (4), the plot of $(R_{\text{obs}} - k_0[S^{\text{IV}}])$ against $1/[\text{OH}^-]$ was linear (Fig. 5), passing through origin. At 30°C , the value of k_2 was found to be $2.05 \times 10^{-2} \text{ dm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ s}^{-1}$.

The rate of reaction was not influenced by a variation in ionic strength in the range 0.1–1.0 mol dm^{-3} using NaNO_3 . The overall empirical activation energy was found to be 30 kJ mol^{-1} .

In several transition metal catalysed autoxidation reactions of sulfur(IV) involving redox cycle of the type $\text{M}^{\text{II}}/\text{M}^{(\text{n}-1)+}$ viz. $\text{Co}^{\text{III}}/\text{Co}^{\text{II}}$, $\text{Ag}^{\text{I}}/\text{Ag}^0$, $\text{Mn}^{\text{III}}/\text{Mn}^{\text{II}}$, $\text{Fe}^{\text{III}}/\text{Fe}^{\text{II}}$, etc., the free radical scavengers like methanol, ethanol and benzene and other compounds one known to inhibit the

Fig. 4. Variation of R_{obs} vs $[S^{\text{IV}}]$ at different $[\text{Os}^{\text{VIII}}]$ at pH = 8.78 and $t = 30^\circ\text{C}$: (\bullet) $[\text{Os}^{\text{VIII}}] = 1 \times 10^{-7} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$; (Δ) $[\text{Os}^{\text{VIII}}] = 2 \times 10^{-7} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$, (o) $[\text{Os}^{\text{VIII}}] = 5 \times 10^{-7} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$.

Fig. 5. The variation of R_{obs} vs $1/[\text{OH}^-]$ at different $[\text{Os}^{\text{VIII}}]$ and $[S^{\text{IV}}]$ and $t = 30^\circ\text{C}$: (\bullet) $[\text{Os}^{\text{VIII}}] = 1 \times 10^{-7} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$, $[S^{\text{IV}}] = 5 \times 10^{-4} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$, (o) $[\text{Os}^{\text{VIII}}] = 1 \times 10^{-7} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$, $[S^{\text{IV}}] = 2 \times 10^{-3} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$, (Δ) $[\text{Os}^{\text{VIII}}] = 2 \times 10^{-7} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$, $[S^{\text{IV}}] = 1 \times 10^{-3} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$.

autoxidation^{9,11,13,15,32-37} by scavenging oxysulfur radicals, SO_5^- , SO_3^- and SO_4^- . The effect of ethanol and benzene was studied to know whether a radical mechanism operated or not. The addition of benzene and ethanol introduced an induction period after which the reaction occurred normally.

The observance of induction period may be due to several reasons. It may be due to preferential oxidation of inhibitors; ethanol¹⁹ is known to be oxidized by osmium(VIII). In addition the latter may form an unreactive or less reactive complex with osmium(VI) and may interfere in its reoxidation. Incidentally, complex formation between osmium(VI) and methanol is reported²⁸. Further the reoxidation of osmium(VI) may involve free radicals as proposed in case of copper(II)-catalysed autoxidation³⁷ for which an intermediate $(\text{O}_2^-)\text{Cu}^{\text{II}}(\text{SO}_3^-)$ has been proposed and a similar intermediate $(\text{O}_2^-)\text{Os}^{\text{VI}}(\text{SO}_3^-)$ may be formed in our case. The radicals O_2^- and SO_3^- are known to be scavenged by inhibitors¹.

In catalysed oxidation reactions only trace amounts of osmium(VIII) are used, whereas in non-catalytic oxidations stoichiometric amounts are necessary. In both cases, the formation of an inner-sphere intermediate complex between the substrate and osmium(VIII) appears to be *a priori*¹⁹. Subsequently, the intermediate complex undergoes internal redox reaction to form oxidation product and osmium(VI). In case of catalysed reactions¹⁹, osmium(VIII) is regenerated with the help of a co-oxidant like H_2O_2 , periodate, hexacyanoferrate, chloramine-T, oxygen, etc.

Since the oxidation of sulfur(IV) by osmium(VIII) has been shown to occur and the fast oxidation of osmium(VI) by O_2 in the pH region 8–10 is well known^{18,38,39}, mechanism involving $\text{Os}^{\text{VIII}}/\text{Os}^{\text{VI}}$ redox cycle is likely to operate in our system.

Before presenting the mechanism, it is necessary to consider the nature of species of osmium(VIII) and sulfur(IV). In aqueous solution, sulfur(IV) mainly exists as $\text{SO}_2 \cdot \text{H}_2\text{O}$, HSO_3^- and SO_3^{2-} governed by equilibria (5, 6) which suggest

that in the pH range 4.6–5.9 maintained for study in acetate buffered medium, sulfur(IV) will dominantly exist as HSO_3^- , and in the pH range 7.9–8.8 used in phosphate buffered alkaline medium it will be almost wholly as SO_3^{2-} .

In acidic aqueous solutions, osmium(VIII) is reported to exist as a weak acid, $\text{OsO}_4(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2$, for which the first and

second dissociation constants are reported to be 8×10^{-3} and 3×10^{-15} respectively. Obviously, in acetate buffered medium, it will exist predominantly in undissociated form. In aqueous alkaline medium, osmium(VIII) is reported to exist as *trans*- $[\text{OsO}_4(\text{OH})(\text{H}_2\text{O})]^-$ and *trans*- $[\text{OsO}_4(\text{HO})_2]^{2-}$ governed¹⁸ by following equilibria (7, 8).

The estimated values of K_1 and K_2 are 4.4×10^3 and 24 respectively^{20,40}. In the weakly alkaline media, as used in this study, these values will require the dominant species to be undissociated molecule, $\text{OsO}_4(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2$. On the contrary, in the similar media osmium(VIII) is reported⁴¹ to exist largely as octahedral species, $[\text{OsO}_4(\text{OH})(\text{H}_2\text{O})]^-$ and our results are in agreement with this suggestion.

To explain the observed experimental rate law, particularly the inverse $[\text{OH}^-]$ -dependence, the following mechanism is proposed for catalysed autoxidation in alkaline medium.

The complex formation involving a minor sulfur(IV) species, HSO_3^- , has to be assumed per force to explain the inverse $[\text{OH}^-]$ -dependence. In the alkaline medium, sulfur(IV) almost wholly exists as SO_3^{2-} and a reaction of the type (14)

between two dominant species will not explain the observed $[\text{OH}^-]$ -dependence, unless the protonation of $[\text{OsO}_4(\text{OH})(\text{SO}_3)]^{3-}$ prior to redox reaction within the complex is assumed. Moreover, an equilibrium of the type involving a replacement of OH^- group is most unlikely.

Interestingly, in the study on the formation of sulfite complex with $[\text{Pd}(\text{Et}_4\text{dien})\text{OH}_2]^{2+}$ and $[\text{Pd}(\text{Et}_4\text{dien})\text{OH}]^+$ only former was found to form $\text{Pd}(\text{Etdien})\text{SO}_3$, the latter being inert due to substitutionally inert nature of hydroxo complexes⁴².

The oxidation of Os^{VI} by O_2 and H_2O_2 in alkaline medium is known to be fast³⁸. Similarly, the oxidation of SO_3^{2-} by H_2O_2 is also a well studied fast reaction^{9,43}. On the basis of the steps (9, 10), the rate law (16) for catalytic pathway may be derived.

$$R_{\text{cat}} = \frac{kK[\text{Os}^{\text{VIII}}][\text{S}^{\text{IV}}][\text{H}^+]}{[\text{H}^+] + K_{\text{d}(2)}} \quad (16)$$

Since $[\text{H}^+] \ll K_{\text{d}(2)}$, the rate law (16) reduces to eq. (17).

$$R_{\text{cat}} = \left(\frac{kK}{K_{\text{d}(2)}}\right) [\text{Os}^{\text{VIII}}][\text{S}^{\text{IV}}][\text{H}^+] \quad (17)$$

On replacing $[\text{H}^+]$ by $K_w/[\text{OH}^-]$, the eq. (17) modifies to eq. (18).

$$R_{\text{cat}} = \frac{kKK_w}{K_{\text{d}(2)}} \frac{[\text{Os}^{\text{VIII}}][\text{S}^{\text{IV}}]}{[\text{OH}^-]} \quad (18)$$

In several catalytic studies^{24-26,30,31,44-46}, the rate law for uncatalysed reaction has been found to be eq. (19).

$$R_{\text{un}} = k_0[\text{S}^{\text{IV}}] \quad (19)$$

On combining the rate laws (18) and (19), the complete rate law (20) which is same as experimental rate law (4), is obtained,

$$R_{\text{obs}} = k_0[\text{S}^{\text{IV}}] + \frac{kKK_w}{K_{\text{d}(2)}} \frac{[\text{Os}^{\text{VIII}}][\text{S}^{\text{IV}}]}{[\text{OH}^-]} \quad (20)$$

through $k_2 = \frac{kKK_w}{K_{\text{d}(2)}}$.

Kinetics in acetate buffered acidic medium :

Although oxygen as co-oxidant is necessary for catalysed autoxidation, the order in its concentration was found to be zero in acid medium also. The kinetics results of variation in $[\text{Os}^{\text{VIII}}]$ and $[\text{S}^{\text{IV}}]$ at fixed pH were in agreement with the rate law (21).

$$R_{\text{obs}} = k_2[\text{Os}^{\text{VIII}}][\text{S}^{\text{IV}}]^2 \quad (21)$$

Unlike autoxidation in alkaline medium, the term corresponding to uncatalysed reaction was absent. This is due to its low rate in acidic media and relatively lower contribution to total rate as compared to the catalysed reaction^{45,46}.

The results of $[\text{Os}^{\text{VIII}}]$ and $[\text{S}^{\text{IV}}]$ -variations were in agreement with the rate law (21) as shown in Figs. 6 and 7. k_2 value of $1.76 \times 10^4 \text{ dm}^6 \text{ mol}^{-2} \text{ s}^{-1}$ determined from $[\text{Os}^{\text{VIII}}]$ -variation was in excellent agreement with the value of $1.89 \times 10^4 \text{ dm}^6 \text{ mol}^{-2} \text{ s}^{-1}$ determined from variation in $[\text{S}^{\text{IV}}]$ at pH 5.22 and 30°C.

Fig. 6. The variation of R_{obs} with $[\text{Os}^{\text{VIII}}]$ at different $[\text{S}^{\text{IV}}]$, pH = 5.22 and $t = 30^\circ\text{C}$: (Δ) $[\text{S}^{\text{IV}}] = 2 \times 10^{-3} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$, (\circ) $[\text{S}^{\text{IV}}] = 4 \times 10^{-3} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$, (\bullet) $[\text{S}^{\text{IV}}] = 8 \times 10^{-3} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$.

Whereas in alkaline medium rate decreased on increasing pH in the region 7.9–8.8, in acidic medium the rate, on the contrary, increased on increasing pH in the range 4.6–5.9. The plot of R_{obs} versus $[\text{H}^+]^{-1}$ was linear (Fig. 8) passing through origin. On including $[\text{H}^+]$ -dependence, the rate law (21) becomes eq. (22).

$$R_{\text{obs}} = \frac{k_3[\text{Os}^{\text{VIII}}][\text{S}^{\text{IV}}]^2}{[\text{H}^+]} \quad (22)$$

which is equivalent to rate law (21) through $k_2 = k_3/[\text{H}^+]$. The value of k_3 was found to be $1.55 \times 10^{-1} \text{ dm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ s}^{-1}$ at 30°C.

The rate of reaction was not affected by the addition of mannitol, a well known free radical scavenger. A variation in ionic strength in the range 0.1–1.0 mol dm^{-3} with sodium nitrate did not influence the rate of the autoxidation. The overall apparent energy of activation was found to be 58 kJ mol^{-1} . Before presenting mechanism, it is necessary to dis-

Fig. 7. Plot of R_{obs} vs $[S^{\text{IV}}]^2$ at different $[\text{Os}^{\text{VIII}}]$, pH = 5.22 and $t = 30^\circ\text{C}$: (o) $[\text{Os}^{\text{VIII}}] = 2.5 \times 10^{-6} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$, (Δ) $[\text{Os}^{\text{VIII}}] = 5.0 \times 10^{-6} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$, (\bullet) $[\text{Os}^{\text{VIII}}] = 8.0 \times 10^{-6} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$.

Discuss some noteworthy points of this study. First, the order in sulfur(IV) is two, which requires the presence of two sulfur(IV) ions in the transition state along with osmium(VIII). The similarity in UV-visible spectra of Os^{VIII} in water and in hexane solutions has been adduced as an evidence of tetrahedral structure of OsO_4 in water solution²⁷. In presence of ligands such as OH^- in alkaline medium, osmium(VIII) acquires an octahedral configuration²⁷. Likewise, in acetate buffered medium, osmium(VIII) is expected to be present as $\text{OsO}_4(\text{L})_2$, where L = sulfur(IV) or acetate or H_2O .

Second, there is spectrophotometric evidence for the formation of a 1 : 1 complex between HSO_3^- and osmium(VI), latter being formed by reduction of osmium(VIII). This requires that out of two sulfur(IV) moieties coordinated to osmium(VIII), one must be HSO_3^- , and in order to be consistent with observed $[\text{H}^+]$ -dependence other should be SO_3^{2-} .

Third, the appearance of pink colour only in presence of O_2 suggests the formation of a $\text{S}^{\text{IV}}\text{-Os}^{\text{VI}}\text{-O}_2$ complex, which is in line with the well known fact that in many reactions presence of SO_3^{2-} in coordination sphere of metal helps

Fig. 8. The variation of pH at different $[\text{Os}^{\text{VIII}}]$ and $[\text{S}^{\text{VI}}]$ and at 30°C : (Δ) $[\text{Os}^{\text{VIII}}] = 2.5 \times 10^{-6} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$, $[\text{S}^{\text{VI}}] = 2 \times 10^{-3} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$, (o) $[\text{Os}^{\text{VIII}}] = 5.0 \times 10^{-6} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$, $[\text{S}^{\text{VI}}] = 2 \times 10^{-3} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$, (\bullet) $[\text{Os}^{\text{VIII}}] = 2.5 \times 10^{-6} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$, $[\text{S}^{\text{VI}}] = 4 \times 10^{-3} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$.

in the binding of O_2 with metal centre^{9,10} and may also help in fast oxidation of metal centre to higher oxidation state through internal oxidation-reduction.

Fourth, the blue colour, which masks pink colour and persists till the end of the reaction, is most likely due to well known blue complex^{47,48} $[\text{OsO}_2(\text{O}_2\text{CCH}_3)_3]^-$.

On the basis of these arguments, following mechanism for autoxidation in acetate buffered medium may be proposed.

The reaction (26) is followed by a large number of possible

fast reactions, some of which, in unbalanced form, are as follows :

In fact the mechanism is much more complicated than visualised here and ignores the structure of coordination sphere of osmium species. Keeping in view that in acid medium sulfur(IV) is almost wholly present as SO_3H^- ion, the following rate law (36) may be derived.

$$R_{\text{obs}} = \frac{k_4 K_3 K_4 K_5 [\text{Os}^{\text{VIII}}] [\text{S}^{\text{IV}}]^2 [\text{H}^+]}{([\text{H}^+] + K_{d(2)})^2} \quad (36)$$

Since in the pH range 4.6–5.9, $[\text{H}^+] \gg K_{d(2)}$, the rate law (36) reduces to

$$R_{\text{obs}} = \frac{k_4 K_3 K_4 K_5 [\text{Os}^{\text{VIII}}] [\text{S}^{\text{IV}}]^2}{[\text{H}^+]} \quad (37)$$

which is same as experimental rate law (22) through $k_3 = k_4 K_3 K_4 K_5$.

Table 3. R_{obs} values for osmium(VIII)-catalysed autoxidation of sulfur(IV) in acidic medium at 30°C

$10^5 [\text{Os}^{\text{VIII}}]$ mol dm ⁻³	$10^3 [\text{S}^{\text{IV}}]$ mol dm ⁻³	pH	$10^6 R_{\text{obs}}$ mol dm ⁻³ s ⁻¹
0.25	2.0	5.22	0.23
0.50	2.0	5.22	0.43
0.75	2.0	5.22	0.66
1.00	2.0	5.22	1.17
2.50	2.0	5.22	2.70
0.25	4.0	5.22	0.83
0.50	4.0	5.22	1.25
0.75	4.0	5.22	1.96
1.00	4.0	5.22	2.97
2.75	4.0	5.22	7.91
0.10	8.0	5.22	1.15
0.20	8.0	5.22	2.15
0.30	8.0	5.22	3.51

Table-3 (contd.)

0.375	8.0	5.22	4.15
0.50	8.0	5.22	5.62
0.25	2.0	5.22	0.23
0.25	3.0	5.22	0.40
0.25	4.0	5.22	0.78
0.25	7.0	5.22	2.50
0.25	8.0	5.22	3.20
0.50	2.0	5.22	0.38
0.50	3.0	5.22	0.67
0.50	5.0	5.22	2.08
0.50	6.0	5.22	3.10
0.50	8.0	5.22	5.85
0.80	1.0	5.22	0.23
0.80	2.0	5.22	0.66
0.80	4.0	5.22	2.25
0.80	6.0	5.22	5.86
0.80	8.0	5.22	10.2
0.25	2.0	5.05	0.15
0.25	2.0	5.22	0.23
0.25	2.0	5.29	0.28
0.25	2.0	5.80	0.852
0.25	2.0	5.90	1.07
0.25	4.0	4.90	0.53
0.25	4.0	5.40	1.74
0.25	4.0	5.50	2.30
0.25	4.0	5.76	3.85
0.25	4.0	5.86	4.75
0.50	2.0	5.05	0.46
0.50	2.0	5.29	0.78
0.50	2.0	5.58	1.76
0.50	2.0	5.72	2.10
0.50	2.0	5.90	3.24

In the step (25) the protonation of one SO_3^{2-} may not look unique, if it is recalled that a similar behaviour has been noted earlier in the study of the aquation of $\text{Pd}(\text{Etdien})\text{SO}_3$ complex⁴².

A comparison of the rates in acidic and alkaline media under similar reaction conditions shows the rate to be much higher in alkaline medium than in acidic medium (Fig. 9). The results of the present study show the osmium(VIII) to be an efficient catalyst in trace concentrations for the autoxidation of sulfur(IV) in alkaline medium. Since the alkaline medium is generally used for desulfurization of flue gases in wet scrubbers, it is possible to adopt osmium(VIII) as a catalyst for removal of SO_2 . However,

Fig. 9. The rate of Os^{VIII} catalyzed autoxidation in acid and alkaline media at [Os^{VIII}] = 1 × 10⁻⁷ mol dm⁻³ and [S^{IV}] = 2 × 10⁻³ mol dm⁻³: (●) acetate buffer, (○) phosphate buffer.

the toxicity of the osmium would be a discouraging factor and has to be overcome by appropriate safety measures.

Although the proposed mechanisms for osmium(VIII)-catalysed autoxidation in acidic and alkaline media are consistent with the observed kinetics as also with the known chemistry of Os^{VIII}, Os^{VI}, sulfur(IV) and other similar systems, we believe that more work is required on Os^{VIII}-S^{IV} and Os^{VI}-S^{IV}-O₂ systems using fast reaction and other spectroscopic techniques to clarify the intimate mechanism of this system.

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